

Agent-based modeling of diversity, new information and minority groups in opinion formation: Online Appendix

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Introduction

Presented here is a sensitivity analysis in support of the main article, *Agent-based modeling of diversity, new information and minority groups in opinion formation*. The sensitivity analysis obtains results using a range of parameter values, to explore general model behavior and the robustness of findings. For a sensitivity analysis of the original model, we refer the reader to Baumann et al. (2020). In our sensitivity analysis, we focus on parameters relating to tendencies, which were not present in the original model of Baumann et al. (2020).

We are interested in how parameter values affect findings in the main article for the research questions, which are repeated below for clarity:

RQ1 Can heterogeneous opinion tendencies change global opinion in consensus, radicalization and polarization?

RQ2 Can different changes in the tendencies of minority groups have different effects on majority opinion?

For clarity also, Tables 1 and 2 from the main article are repeated here as Tables [A1](#) and [A2](#), which show the model trials and baseline parameter values.

Method

A sensitivity analysis was performed for the effect of sociality K and tendency magnitude T on the comparisons of Trials D–F (i.e. with non-zero tendencies) with control Trials A–C (i.e. with 0 tendencies). Sociality was

Trial	α	β	T	Description
A	0.05	2	0	Consensus
B	3	0	0	Radicalization
C	3	3	0	Polarization
D	0.05	2	± 0.5	Trial A variant: opposing constant groups
E	3	0	± 0.5	Trial B variant: opposing constant groups
F	3	3	± 0.5	Trial C variant: opposing constant groups
G	3	3	0	Trial C variant: single pulse minority group
H	3	3	0	Trial C variant: single ramp minority group
I	3	3	0	Trial C variant: opposing pulse minority groups

Table A1: Model trials and baseline parameter values. For all trials, $K = 3$, $m = 10$, $r = 0.5$, $\gamma = 2.1$ and $\epsilon = 0.01$. Parameter T is the constant tendency magnitude for the majority group, i.e. $|\dot{x}_j|$ in Equation 4. Baseline minority group parameter values are given in Table A2.

Parameter description	Parameter value
Minority group size (fraction)	0.05
Pulse amplitude	2
Pulse time duration	500
Pulse onset time	0
Opposing pulse time delay (Trials G–H)	N/A
Opposing pulse time delay (Trial I)	100

Table A2: Baseline parameter values for minority groups. Minority group size is expressed as a fraction of all agents, where 0.002 is 1 agent in 500.

varied consistently for Trials D–F and Trials A–C, but since non-zero tendency only existed for Trials D–F, the corresponding results for Trials A–C remained constant.

A sensitivity analysis was also performed for the effect of minority group parameters on the comparisons of Trials G and I with control Trial C. Trial H was omitted from the sensitivity analysis due to the similarity with Trial G results. Parameter values were varied for minority group size, pulse amplitude, onset time and duration for Trial G, and opposing pulse time delay for Trial I. Trial C results remained constant since it lacked any minority group.

The range and spacing of parameter values were chosen to explore param-

ters relative to the baseline for each. In presenting results for the sensitivity analysis, confidence bands for mean values were plotted assuming normality, and the Hettmansperger-Sheather method was used for the confidence bands for median values (Hettmansperger & Sheather, 1986). Statistical test p values were plotted alongside these results, noting that significance can be unclear from confidence bands (Krzywinski & Altman, 2013). Please see the main article for descriptions of the statistical tests used.

Results for the sensitivity analysis were aggregated over 16 repetitions for each trial and sensitivity case. The main outcome of interest for the sensitivity analysis was the final agent opinions. Opinion dynamics were additionally plotted with the tendency group of agents to help interpret the results, using the same approach to aggregation and confidence bands as described in the main article. Figures for the sensitivity analysis are summarized as:

- Figure [A1](#): Sensitivity analysis of sociality and constant tendency magnitude for the same comparisons as shown in Figure 3 of the main article, i.e. results for RQ1. Opinion magnitudes were used for reasons of symmetry for consensus and polarization, as discussed in the main article.
- Figures [A2–A4](#): Opinion dynamics from the sensitivity analysis of constant tendency magnitudes, i.e. further exploration of results in Figure [A1d–A1f](#).
- Figure [A5](#): Sensitivity analysis of minority group tendency parameters for the same comparisons as shown in Figure 6 of the main article, i.e. results for RQ2.
- Figures [A6–A10](#): Opinion dynamics from the sensitivity analysis of minority group parameters, i.e. further exploration of results in Figure [A5](#).

Results

Constant tendencies

Figure [A1a–A1c](#) shows the effect of sociality parameter K on Trials D–F compared against Trials A–C. Figure [A1d–A1f](#) shows equivalent results for varying tendency magnitude T .

A generally linear relationship is found for final agent opinion with parameters K and T . However, results in Figure [A1e](#) for radicalization show less straightforward behavior, as discussed below with opinion dynamics. The difference between mean and median final opinion is evident here, where

Figure A1: Sensitivity analysis comparing unbiased Trials A–C against those with heterogeneous tendency in Trials D–F, varying parameter values one at a time. Plots (a–c) show sensitivity to sociality parameter K , where (a) is for consensus (Trials A and D), (b) is for radicalization (Trials B and E), and (c) is for polarization (Trials C and F). Plots (d–f) show sensitivity to tendency magnitude T in Trials D–F. Lines show the average final opinions as a function of the changing parameter value, corresponding to the left-hand vertical axis, with 95% confidence bands calculated separately for the mean and median. Lines are colored according to each trial, consistent with other comparison figures. The horizontal lines for Trials A–C in plots (d–f) are due to parameter insensitivity, i.e. the parameter is not present. Markers show statistical test probabilities, corresponding to the right-hand vertical axis. Baseline parameter values are highlighted in bold on the horizontal axis and can be compared directly to results in Figure 3.

Figure A2: Opinion dynamics for consensus (Trial D) with random constant tendencies of $\pm T$, shown with different values of T , as indicated by the subplot titles. Lines are colored according to the tendency groups (group 0 has $-T$ tendency, and group 1 has $+T$ tendency).

Figure A3: Opinion dynamics for radicalization (Trial E) with random constant tendencies of $\pm T$, shown with different values of T , as indicated by the subplot titles. Lines are colored according to the tendency groups (group 0 has $-T$ tendency, and group 1 has $+T$ tendency).

Figure A4: Opinion dynamics for polarization (Trial F) with random constant tendencies of $\pm T$, shown with different values of T , as indicated by the subplot titles. Lines are colored according to the tendency groups (group 0 has $-T$ tendency, and group 1 has $+T$ tendency).

only the mean is used to force radicalization to be in the positive direction, as explained in the main article. Of note is that bootstraps are used by the plotting method to obtain average values.

Opinion dynamics in the sensitivity analysis are plotted in Figures A2–A4 for consensus, radicalization and polarization respectively, i.e. Trials D–F with varying T . Figures A2 and 4 demonstrate marked similarities between consensus and polarization with opposing tendencies, consistent with results presented in the main article.

Figure A3 shows slightly different behavior to the main article for radicalization with diverse tendencies, as discussed above with final opinions. With small tendency magnitudes, (i.e. T within the initial opinion range), radicalization is similar to that found with 0 tendency, just with divergence of the 2 groups, as noted in the main article with $T = 0.5$. However, with larger T , tendency differences between groups increasingly dominate results, which more closely resemble the divergent behavior of split consensus (Figures 2a and A2). The upshot is that radicalization is no longer entirely recognizable when large opposing tendencies are present, although there is still evidence of coordination between the opposing groups (shown by the parallel fluctuations of groups in Figure A3), which is not present in split consensus or biased polarization (Figures A2 and A4). These results are consistent with Figure A1.

Minority group tendencies

Figure A5 shows the effect of minority group parameters for Trial G (single transient pulse) and Trial I (delayed opposing pulse) compared against Trial C (the equivalent trial in the absence of any minority group). These show that:

- Minority group size has a roughly linear effect on majority final opinion when at least 5% of agents are in the minority group (Figure A5a). There is also an observable effect when there is at least 1 agent in the minority group (0.002 as a fraction of all 500 agents, which is the leftmost data point), i.e. the minority group has a significant effect regardless of group size.
- For pulse amplitude larger than 0.01, results are relatively insensitive to the amplitude (Figure A5b), i.e. the minority group has a significant effect regardless of its amplitude.
- Above 1 time step, results are relatively insensitive to pulse duration

Figure A5: Sensitivity analysis comparing unbiased Trial C against Trial G with a single minority group, and Trial I with 2 opposing minority groups, varying parameter values one at a time. Plots (a-d) show sensitivity to parameters for the single minority group, namely (a) minority group size, (b) pulse amplitude, (c) time duration and (d) start time. Plot (e) shows sensitivity to the time delay between opposing group pulses, and plot (f) compares Trial I against Trial G instead of Trial C. Lines show the average final opinions as a function of the changing parameter values, corresponding to the left-hand vertical axis, with 95% confidence bands calculated separately for the mean and median. Lines are colored according to each trial, consistent with other comparison figures. The horizontal line for Trial C in plots (a-e) is due to parameter insensitivity, i.e. none of the shown parameters is present, and the same explanation applies to Trial G in plot (f). Markers show statistical test probabilities, corresponding to the right-hand vertical axis. Baseline parameter values are highlighted in bold on the horizontal axis and can be compared directly to results in Figure 6.

Figure A6: Opinion dynamics for Trial G with different minority group sizes, as indicated by the subplot titles. Tendency group 0 is the majority group, and group 1 the minority group.

Figure A7: Opinion dynamics for Trial G with different pulse amplitudes, as indicated by subplot titles. Tendency group 0 is the majority group, and group 1 the minority group.

Figure A8: Opinion dynamics for Trial G with different pulse durations, as indicated by subplot titles. Tendency group 0 is the majority group, and group 1 the minority group.

Figure A9: Opinion dynamics for Trial G with different pulse durations, as indicated by subplot titles. Tendency group 0 is the majority group, and group 1 the minority group.

Figure A10: Opinion dynamics for Trial I with different opposing pulse time delays, as indicated by subplot titles. Tendency group 0 is the majority group, group 1 the minority group, and group 2 the delayed opposing minority group.

(Figure A5c), i.e. the minority group has a significant effect regardless of its duration.

- Results show slight sensitivity to pulse onset time (Figure A5d), i.e. the minority group has a significant effect regardless of its onset time, except if it is around half way through the simulated time period, where the effect is no longer significant, as considered further below.
- Results are relatively sensitive to the opposing pulse time delay (Figure A5a), i.e. the second group does not cancel out the first, except at around 10 and 200 time steps delay, where the effect on the majority is no longer significant, as considered further below. Notably, the two groups do not appear to cancel out even when there is no delay in their behaviors, as also discussed further below.
- Differences between Trials G and I (Figure A5f) follow a similar pattern to differences between Trials C and I (Figure A5e). However, differences are generally not significant between Trials G and I, unlike between Trials C and I. These results are explored further in Figures A6–A10 as time series. It is evident in Figure A6 that having at least 1% of agents in the minority group enables it to move away from the majority group, and the minority group has a bigger effect as it increases in size. Figure A7 shows that a pulse amplitude greater than 1 (i.e. outside the initial opinion range) similarly enables the minority group to move away from the majority group, and the effect on the majority group also grows with increasing amplitude. Figure A8 shows that a pulse duration beyond around 50 time steps is able to produce an observable effect on the majority, but there is variability in this across different durations; short durations may be too short to have any effect, whereas with long durations it appears possible that opinions in the minority group may become too far from the majority to be homophilous. Figure A9 shows that an onset time of 500 time steps appears too late to have any real influence on the majority, while stochastic effects are likely to explain why even later onsets appear able to have a greater effect. Figure A10 shows that different sizes of opposing time delays have a notable effect on opinion dynamics, but effects on final opinion in the majority group are generally very similar. The reduced effect on the majority with delays of 10 and 200 time steps is reflected in the time series, and the increased effect at 50 and 500 time steps is also evident in the time series. The significant positive effect with 0 time delay warrants further investigation, as in theory the system is completely symmetrical. However, the system

is particularly sensitive to stochastic effects in this case, due to the exaggerating effects of the two minority groups at time 0, meaning bias is expected in a single direction which depends on random initial conditions. More repetitions are likely to give a more reliable average result, but it appears the simultaneous opposing groups do not cancel out, and instead have an unpredictable effect similar to radicalization. These results are consistent with Figure A5.

Discussion

Results for the sensitivity analysis are supportive of the findings presented in the main article. The model displays an appropriate level of sensitivity to parameter values, and the findings reported in the main article are not highly dependent on these at a qualitative level.

The sensitivity analysis reveals aspects of the model which are worth examining further in future. The high level of variability in Trial C is particularly evident in Figure A5, where variability in the majority group appears reduced by the presence of the minority group(s) in Trials G and I. This may be due to the deterministic nature of the minority group tendency function: although Trial C also had a deterministic tendency (i.e. constant 0), the unbiased nature of such polarization seems to have made it less predictable than with a coordinated influence. It should also be noted that the confidence bands for average final opinion in Trial C, as shown in Figure A5, are larger than for its average magnitude of final opinion, as shown in Figure A1a and A1e, reflecting the greater spread of opinions between the poles, consistent with Figures 3 and 6.

The different vertical axis scales of the subplots in Figures A1 and A5 should be noted when comparing results, including the separate vertical axes for average final opinion and statistical test p values. The number of repetitions inherently affected p values, and the suitability of this approach is discussed further in the main article.

The sensitivity analysis aggregated results across multiple trial repetitions, as described in the main article. However, there are a few examples in the sensitivity analysis which appear particularly affected by stochasticity, particularly in Figure A1e for large tendency magnitude, Figure A6d for large pulse onset time, and Figure A6e for 0 time delay. These would benefit from further investigation, but are not important to the main findings.

The sensitivity analysis presented here has only considered one parameter

at a time, and so does not account for combinations of non-baseline values, i.e. how parameters interact. This is discussed further in the main article.

References

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